

Analysis of Accounting Standards: IFRS & IND AS

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Indian Accounting Standards: A brief

1. Meaning:- Indian Accounting Standards (abbreviated as Ind AS) are a set of accounting standards notified by the Ministry of Corporate Affairs which are converged with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) (IND AS is notified by NACAS on 25th Feb 2011.) (NFRA= National Financial Reporting Authority U/s 132)
2. Applicability of IND AS: - The Ind AS shall be applicable to the companies as follows: As notified by MCA as on 16/02/15 in Companies (Indian Accounting Standards) Rules, 2015.

Obligation to comply with Indian Accounting Standards (Ind AS). - (1) The Companies and their auditors shall comply with the Indian Accounting Standards (Ind AS) specified in Annexure to these rules in preparation of their financial statements and audit respectively, in the following manner.

(i) On voluntary basis	On mandatory basis	
	(ii) Accounting periods beginning on or after 1/4/16(For 31/3/17) with the comparatives.	(iii) Accounting periods beginning on or after 01/04/17(For 31/3/18), with the comparatives.
Accounting periods beginning on or after April 1, 2015, with the comparatives for the periods ending 31 st March, 2015 or thereafter;	A. Companies whose equity and/or debt securities are listed or are in the process of listing on any stock exchange in India or outside India and having net worth* of Rs. 500 Crore or more. B. Companies other than those covered in (ii) (a) above, having net worth of Rs. 500 Crore or more. C. Holding, subsidiary, joint venture or associate Above.	A. Companies whose equity and/or debt securities are listed or are in the process of being listed on any stock exchange in India or outside India. B. Unlisted companies having net worth of 250 Crore or more but less than rupees 500 Crore. C. Holding, subsidiary, joint venture or associate companies of above.

*NET WORTH: "NET WORTH" shall have the meaning assigned to it in clause (57) of section 2 of the Act

"NET WORTH" means the aggregate value of the paid-up share capital and all reserves created out of the profits and securities premium account, after deducting the aggregate value of the accumulated losses, deferred expenditure and miscellaneous expenditure not written off, as per the audited balance sheet, but does not include reserves created out of revaluation of assets, write-back of depreciation and amalgamation.

Note:-

1. Companies listed on SME exchanges shall not be required to apply Ind AS.
2. Once Ind AS is followed by the company, it shall be required to follow, for all the subsequent financial statements.
3. This press realise do not apply on Banking Companies, Insurance Companies and NBFC's

IND AS ROADMAP FOR BANKS, INSURANCE COMPANIES AND NBFCs

- A.** Scheduled commercial banks (excluding RRBs) and insurers/insurance companies:- Mandatory for accounting periods beginning from 1 April 2018 onwards (With Comparative)
- Scheduled commercial banks (excluding RRBs), Insurers/insurance companies
 - Holding, subsidiary, joint venture or associate companies of scheduled commercial banks
- B.** NBFCs: NBFCs will be required to prepare Ind AS based financial statements in two phases.
- Phase 1: Mandatory for accounting periods beginning from 1 April 2018 onwards (With Comparative)
- NBFCs (Whether listed or unlisted) having a net worth of Rs. 500 crore or more
 - Holding, subsidiary, joint venture or associate companies of the above, other than those companies already covered under the corporate roadmap announced by MCA
- *On insurance Company:- Applicable from 01st April 2020(20-21) as notified as on 28/6/17 by IRDA
- Phase 2: Mandatory for accounting periods beginning from 1 April 2019 onwards (With Comparative)
- NBFCs whose equity and/or debt securities are listed or are in the process of listing on any stock exchange.
 - NBFCs that are unlisted companies, having a net worth of 250 crore INR or more but less than 500 Crore INR
 - Holding, subsidiary, joint venture or associate companies of companies covered above, other than those companies already covered under the corporate roadmap announced by MCA
- Voluntary adoption not permitted to BANKS, INSURANCE COMPANIES AND NBFCs
- D.** Companies/entities not covered in the roadmap
- NBFCs having a net worth below 250 crore INR.
 - Urban cooperative banks (UCBs) and RRBs.

NUMBER AND NAME OF IND AS, WITH RESPECTIVE IFRS OR IAS

S. N.	Name of Ind AS with Number	IFRS	IAS
1.	Ind AS 101 First-time Adoption of Indian Accounting Standards	1	
2.	Ind AS 102 Share based Payment	2	
3.	Ind AS 103 Business Combinations	3	
4.	Ind AS 104 Insurance Contracts	4	
5.	Ind AS 105 Non current Assets Held for Sale and Discontinued Operations	5	
6.	Ind AS 106 Exploration for and Evaluation of Mineral Resources	6	
7.	Ind AS 107 Financial Instruments: Disclosures	7	
8.	Ind AS 108 Operating Segments	8	
9.	Ind AS 109 Financial Instruments: Recognition and Measurement issued.	9	
10.	Ind AS 110 Consolidated Financial.	10	
11.	Ind AS 111 Joint Arrangements.	11	
12.	Ind AS 112 Disclosure of Interest in Other.	12	
13.	Ind AS 113 Fair Value Measurement.	13	
14.	Ind AS 114 Regulatory Deferral Accounts.	14	
15.	Ind AS 1 Presentation of Financial Statements		1
16.	Ind AS 2 Inventories		2
17.	Ind AS 7 Statement of Cash Flows		7
18.	Ind AS 8 Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors		8
19.	Ind AS 10 Events after the Reporting Period		10
20.	Ind AS 11 Construction Contracts *		11
21.	Ind AS 12 Income Taxes		12
22.	Ind AS 16 Property, Plant and Equipment		16
23.	Ind AS 17 Leases		17
24.	Ind AS 18 Revenue*		18
25.	Ind AS 19 Employee Benefits		19
26.	Ind AS 20 Accounting for Government Grants and Disclosure of Government Assistance		20
27.	Ind AS 21 The Effects of Changes in Foreign Exchange Rates		21
28.	Ind AS 23 Borrowing Costs		23
29.	Ind AS 24 Related Party Disclosures		24
30.	Ind AS 27 Consolidated and Separate Financial Statements		27
31.	Ind AS 28 Investments in Associates		28
32.	Ind AS 29 Financial Reporting in Hyperinflationary Economies		29
33.	Ind AS 32 Financial Instruments: Presentation		32
34.	Ind AS 33 Earnings per Share		33
35.	Ind AS 34 Interim Financial Reporting		34
36.	Ind AS 36 Impairment of Assets		36
37.	Ind AS 37 Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets		37
38.	Ind AS 38 Intangible Assets		38
39.	Ind AS 40 Investment Property		40
40.	Ind AS 41 Agriculture.		41

PART I: Differences between IND AS and Existing AS**AS 1: Presentation of Financial Statements**

SN	Basis of Differences	IND AS 1: Presentation of Financial Statements	AS 1: Disclosure of Accounting Policy
1	Scope	Deals in presentation of Financial Statements (FS). (Wider scope)	Deals with Disclosure of Accounting Policy (Limited Scope)
2	Explicit Statement of Compliance	Ind AS are complied in the FS. Ind AS 1 allows deviation from a requirement of an IND AS in case the management concludes that compliance with Ind ASs will be misleading and if the regulatory framework requires does not prohibit such a departure.	No Such Provision
3	Current and Non-current Classification	Explained	Not explained
4	Extraordinary Items	Prohibits presentation of any item as Extraordinary Item	Permits presentation of any item as Extraordinary Item
5	Disclosure of Judgements and Assumptions made	Required	No such disclosure explicit.
6	Classification of Expenses	Presented based on nature of expenses	No Such Provision
7	Presentation of Balance Sheet at the beginning of the earliest period	Ind AS 1 requires, when (a) Applies an accounting policy retrospectively or (b) makes a retrospective restatement of items in the financial statements, or (c) when it reclassifies items in its financial statements.	Not Required
8	Disclosure of Reclassified of Items with reason.	Not Required	Required
9	Statement of Changes in Equity	Required	Not Required
10	Statement of Other Comprehensive Income in two sections	Required	Not Required
11	Inclusion of Comparative Information	Required	Not Required
12	Classification of Long-term Loan Arrangement	Long term loan arrangement need not be classified as current on account of breach of a material provision, for which the lender has agreed to waive before the approval of financial statements.	No Such Provision

Ind AS 2: Valuation of Inventory

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 2: Valuation of Inventory	AS 2: Valuation of Inventory
1.	Subsequent Recognition	Subsequent recognition of cost/carrying amount of inventories as an expense.	Does not provide the same
2	Inventory Provider of Service	Explanation with regard to inventories of service providers	Does not Contain such an explanation.
3	Machinery Spares	Does not contain specific explanation in respect of such spares as this aspect is covered under Ind AS 16.	The existing AS 2 explains that inventories do not include spare parts, servicing equipment and standby equipment which meet the definition of PPE as per AS 10. Such items are accounted for in accordance with AS 10.
4	Inventory held by Commodity Broker-traders	Measure their inventories at fair value less costs to sell.	This aspect is not in AS 2.
5	Definition of Fair Value and Distinction Between NRV and Fair Value	Explanation in respect of distinction between net realisable value and fair value.	Does not contain the definition of fair value and such explanation.
6	Subsequent Assessment of NRV	Provides detailed guidance in case of subsequent assessment of NRV. It also deals with the reversal of the write-down of inventories to NRV to the extent of the	Does not deal with such reversal.

		amount of original write-down, & the recognition and disclosure thereof in the financial statements.	
7	Inventories Acquired on Deferred Settlement Terms	A difference between the purchase price for normal credit terms and the amount paid, is recognised as interest expense	No such treatment.
8	Cost Formula	Requires the use of consistent cost formula in determining the cost of an item of inventory.	Does not specifically requires the use of consistent cost formulas

Ind AS 7: Cash Flow Statement

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 7: Cash Flow Statement	AS 3: Cash Flow Statement
1.	Bank Overdraft Repayable on Demand	Bank overdrafts which are repayable on demand as a part of cash and cash equivalents	No Such provision
2	Adjustment of the Profit or Loss for the Effects of Undistributed Profits of Associates and Non-controlling Interests	Requires such adjustment under Indirect Method	No such provision
3	Cash Flows associated with Extraordinary Activities	No items are classified as Extraordinary Activities.	Extraordinary activities to be separately classified as arising from operating, investing and financing activities
4	Disclosure of Cash and Cash Equivalents in Specific Situations	Disclose the amount of cash & cash equivalents and other assets & liabilities in the subsidiaries or other businesses over which control is obtained or lost	No such provision
5	New Examples of Cash Flows arising from Financing Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ cash payments to owners to acquire or redeem the entity's shares ➤ cash proceeds from mortgages ➤ cash payments by a lessee for the reduction of the outstanding liability relating to a finance lease. 	Not included
6	Investment in Subsidiaries, Associates and JVs (Investees)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Mentions the use of equity or cost method ➤ Specifically deals by using equity method 	Not contain such requirements.
7	Use of Different Terminology and Translation of Cash Flows of a Foreign Subsidiary.	Functional currency	Reporting currency
8	Disclosures	Requires more disclosures	No disclosures.

Ind AS 8: Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors

SN	Basis of Differences	IND AS 8: (Accounting Policies, Changes in Accounting Estimates and Errors)	AS 5 (Net Profit or Loss for the Period, Prior Period Items and Changes in Accounting Policies (Revised))
1	Objective	Prescribe the criteria for selecting and changing accounting policies, together with the accounting treatment and disclosure of changes in accounting policies, changes in accounting estimates and corrections of errors	Prescribe the classification and disclosure of certain items in the statement of profit and loss.
2	Basis	Intends to enhance the relevance and reliability of an entity's financial statements and the comparability of those financial statements over time and with the financial statements of other entities	Classification and disclosure of certain items in the statement of profit and loss for uniform preparation and presentation of financial statements
3	Presentations of Extraordinary Items	Prohibits	Provide

4	Definition of Accounting Policies	Broadens the definition to include bases, conventions, rules and practices (in addition to principles) applied by an entity in the preparation and presentation of Financial statements.	Restricts the definition to the specific accounting principles & the methods of applying those principles
5	Change in Accounting Policies if required by statute	Not included.	Included.
6	Retrospective Accounting of Changes in Accounting Policies	Requires that changes in accounting policies should be accounted for with retrospective effect.	Not specify how change in accounting policy should be accounted for.
7	Rectification of Material Prior Period Errors	Rectification of material prior period errors with retrospective effect except where it is impracticable to determine the period specific effects.	Prospective effect

Ind AS 10: Events after the Reporting Period.

SN	Basis of Differences	IND AS 10: Events after the Reporting Period.	Amended AS4: Contingencies and EOABS Date
1	Non Adjusting Events if Material	Disclosed in the financial statements (Disclosed in notes to account.)	Disclosed in the approving authority. Report of
2	Proposed Dividend	Dividend proposed or declared after the reporting Period cannot be recognised as a liability. Disclosed in notes to account.	Now Same.
3	Distribution of non-cash assets to owners	Guideline Given.	No Guidelines.
4	Impact of non-adjusting event in case of a question mark on going concern.	Basis of accounting changes from going concern to liquidation.	No Such Requirement.
5	In case of breach of a material provision of a long term loan arrangement	Considered as an adjusting event (Referred IND AS 1)	No Such Provisions.

Ind AS 11: Construction Contracts

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 11: Constructions Contracts	AS 7: Constructions Contracts
1	Fair Value	Contract revenue shall be measured at fair value of consideration received/receivable	Does not recognise fair value concept
2	Inclusion of Borrowing costs	Ind AS 11 does not specifically make reference to Ind AS 23.	Includes borrowing costs as per AS 16,
3	Accounting for Service Concession arrangements	Appendix A of Ind AS 11 deals with accounting aspects involved in such arrangements & Appendix B deals with disclosures of such arrangements.	Does not deal with accounting for Service Concession Arrangements

Ind AS 12: Income Taxes-(IMPORTANT)

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 12: Income Taxes	AS 22: Accounting for Taxes on Income
1	Approach for creating Deferred Tax	Based on balance sheet approach	Based on income statement approach
2	Recognition of DTA for unabsorbed depreciation or carry forward of losses	Same criteria for recognising deferred tax arising from Unabsorbed depreciation or carry forward of losses as in case of deductible temporary differences.	DTA are recognised only if here should be virtual certainty supported by convincing evidence
3	Disclosure of DTA and DTL in Balance Sheet	Does not deal with this aspect except in accordance with the requirements of Ind AS 1.	Deals with disclosure of DTA and DTL.
4	DTA/DTL arising out of Revaluation of Assets.	Shall be measured on the basis of tax consequences from the sale of asset rather than through use.	Does not deal with this aspect.
5	Guidance for Recognition of Deferred Tax in a Tax Holiday Period	Does not specifically deal with these situations.	Specially Provides guidance regarding recognition of DT in Tax Holiday under Sec 80-IA, 80-IB, 10A & 10B
6	Disclosure Requirements	More detailed.	Less detailed.

IND AS 16:- Property, Plant and Equipment

SN	Basis of Differences	IND AS 16:- Property, Plant and Equipment	Amended AS 10:- PPE
1.	Fixed Assets retired from Active Use and Held for Sale	Ind AS 16 does not deal with the assets 'held for sale' because the treatment of such assets is covered in Ind AS 105, Non-current Assets Held for Sale and Discontinued Operations.	Deals with accounting for items of fixed assets retired from active use and held for sale.
2.	Stripping Costs in the Production Phase of a Surface Mine	Provides guidance on measuring 'Stripping Costs in the Production Phase of a Surface Mine'.	Does not contain this guidance.

Ind AS 17: Leases

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 17: Leases	AS 19: Leases
1	Excludes leases of land from its scope	Does not have exclusion land and has specific provisions dealing with leases of land and building.	Excludes leases of land from its scope
2	Residual Value definition	Deleted	Given
3	Inception of Lease and Commencement of Lease	Makes a distinction between inception of lease and commencement of lease.	No distinction.
4	Current/Non-current Classification	Requires current/non-current classification of lease Liabilities	No such provision.
5	Method of amortisation in case of Sale and Leaseback as finance lease	No amortisation method is given	Deferred profit/loss and amortised in the ratio of depreciation.
6	Accounting for Incentives in the Case of Operating Leases	Guidelines given	No guidelines is given
7	Escalation treatment	In case of lease rental, is in the line with inflation	No provision.

Ind AS 18: Revenue

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 18: Revenue	AS 9: Revenue
1	Definition of Revenue	Broad definition of 'revenue' is given because it covers all economic benefits that arise in the ordinary course of activities of an entity which result in increases in equity, other than increases relating to contributions from equity participants.	Gross inflow of cash, or receivables arising in the course of the ordinary activities of an enterprise from the sale of goods, rendering of services, & interest, Royalties & dividends.
2	Measurement of Revenue	Revenue to be measured at fair value of the consideration received or receivable.	Revenue is recognised at the Nominal amount of consideration receivable.
3	Barter Transactions	Deals with the exchange of goods and services \ with goods and services of similar and dissimilar nature. Specific guidance is given regarding \ barter transactions Involving advertising \ \ services.	This aspect is not dealt with in the existing AS 9
4.	Recognition of Separately Identifiable Components	Guidance on application of recognition criteria to the separately identifiable components of a single transaction in order to reflect the substance of the transaction.	Does not specifically deal with the same.
5	Recognition of Interest	Interest to be recognised using effective interest rate method(EIR) as set out in Ind AS 109, Financial Instruments	Requires the recognition of revenue from interest on time Proportion basis.
6	Guidance Regarding Revenue Recognition in Specific Cases	Provides guidance regarding revenue recognition in case the entity is under any obligation to provide free or discounted goods or services or award credits to its Customers due to any customer loyalty programme.	Does not deal with this aspect.
7	Disclosure of Excise Duty	Does not specifically deal with the same.	Specifically deals with disclosure of excise duty as a deduction from revenue from sales transactions.
8.	Disclosure Requirements	Disclosure requirements are given more.	Less disclosure requirements.

Ind AS 19: Employee Benefits

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 19: Employee Benefits	AS 15: Employee Benefits
1	Constructive Obligations	Employee benefits arising from constructive obligations are also covered	Not deal.
2	Definition of Employee	Includes directors	Includes whole-time directors
3	Contractual Agreement between a Multi- employer Plan and its Participants	Deals with situations where surplus in the plan will be distributed to the participants	Does not deal
4	Qualified Actuary	Encourages, but does not require, involving a qualified Actuary in the measurement of DBO.	Does not specifically encourage the same
5	Actuarial Gains and Losses	Shall be recognised in other comprehensive income	Recognised in the profit & loss
6	Financial Assumptions	Shall be based on market expectations.	Does not clarify the same.
7	Timing of Recognition of Termination Benefits	More guidance has been given.	-----

Ind AS 20: Accounting for Government Grants and Disclosure of Government Assistance

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 20: Accounting for Government Grants and Disclosure of Government Assistance	AS 12: Accounting for Government Grants
1	Grant in respect of Non Depreciable Assets	Grants should be recognised as income over the periods which bear the cost of meeting the obligation.	Shown as capital reserve which is a part of shareholders' funds
2	Government Grants in the Nature of Promoters Contribution	Grants should be recognised as income over the periods which bear the cost of meeting the obligation.	Shown as capital reserve which is a part of shareholders' funds
3	Grant in kind given Free or at a Concessional Rate	Recorded at a Fair value	Recorded at a nominal value
4	Government Assistance	Deals with Government Assistance	Not deals
5	Return of grant.	Considered as change in Accounting Estimates.	Treated as extraordinary items
6	Loans at Concessional Rate	A below-market rate of interest should be recognised as grant.	No provision given.

Ind AS 21: The Effects of Changes in Foreign Exchange Rates

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 21: The Effects of Changes in Foreign Exchange Rates	AS 11: The Effects of Changes in Foreign Exchange Rates
1	Forward Exchange Contracts & other similar Financial Instruments	Excludes from its scope forward exchange contracts and other similar financial instruments, which are treated in accordance with Ind AS 109.	Does not such exclude accounting for such contracts.
2	Exchange Differences arising on Translation of Certain Long-term Monetary Items from Foreign Currency to Functional Currency.	Does not apply to long-term foreign currency monetary items recognised in the financial statements before the beginning of the first Ind AS financial reporting period as per the previous GAAP, i.e. AS 11. However, as provided in Ind AS 101, such an entity may continue to apply the accounting policy so opted for such long-term foreign currency monetary items as per the previous GAAP.	Gives an option to recognise such exchange differences directly in equity, to be transferred to profit or loss over the life of the relevant liability/asset if such items are not related to acquisition of fixed assets. The FED related to fixed assets can be recognised as part of the cost of the asset.
3	Approach for Translation	Based on the functional currency approach.	Based on IFO & NIFO approach for accounting for a foreign operation.
4	Presentation Currency	Presentation currency can be different from local currency and it gives detailed guidance in this regard	Does not explicitly state so.

Ind AS 23: Borrowing Costs

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 23: Borrowing Costs	AS 16: Borrowing Costs
1	Scope (Relaxation in Capitalization)	Borrowing cost need not be capitalised ➤ Inventories that are manufactured or otherwise produced, in large quantities on a repetitive basis.	Does not provide for such relaxation scope
2	Reporting in Hyperinflationary Economies	Part of the borrowing costs that compensates for inflation should be expensed, not capitalized in respect of qualifying assets.	No Such Standard in India.
3	Capitalization Rate	Requires Disclosure of Capitalisation Rate	Does not require
4	Effective interest Method	Interest expenses to be computed by using of effective interest Method.	No Such Requirement.

Ind AS 24: Related Party Disclosures

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 24: Related Party Disclosures	AS 18: Related Party Disclosures
1.	Definition of Relative	Uses the term – a close member of the family of a person.	Uses the term – relatives of an individual.
2	Relative covers	Children, spouse or domestic partner, brother, sister, father and mother; children of that person's spouse or domestic partner; and dependants of that person or that person's spouse or domestic partner.	Covers the spouse, son, daughter, brother, sister, father and mother
3	KMP	Covers KMP of the parent as well	KMP of the entity only
4	Related Parties in case of Joint Venture	Co-venturers or co-associates are related to each other.	Co-venturers or co-associates are not related to each other
5	Post-employment Benefits	Specifically includes post-employment benefit plans for the benefit of employees of an entity or its related entity as related parties.	Does not specifically cover entities that are post-employment benefit plans, as related parties
6	Next Most Senior Parent	Additional disclosure is required for such parent.	No such provision.
7	Disclosure for Compensation	Extended disclosures for compensation of KMP under different categories.	Not required.
8	Disclosure of 'Amount of the Transactions' vs 'Volume of the Transactions'	The amount of the transactions need to be disclosed	Option to disclose the - Volume of the transactions either as an amount or as an appropriate proportion
9	Government Related Entities	Disclosures of certain information by the government related entities.	Presently exempts the disclosure of such information

Ind AS 33: Earnings Per Share

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 33: Earnings Per Share	AS 20: Earnings Per Share
1	Disclosure of EPS with & Without Extraordinary Items	No Requirement	Requirement
2	Basic and Diluted EPS from Continuing and Discontinued Operations	Requires presentation of basic and diluted EPS from continuing and discontinued operations separately	Not require any such disclosure
3	Options held by the Entity on its Shares	Specifically deal with options held by the entity on its shares	Not deals.

Ind AS 34: Interim Financial Reporting

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 34: Interim Financial Reporting	AS 25: Interim Financial Reporting
1.	Condensed statement of change in equity	Required with condensed BS, PL and Cash Flow.	Not Required with condensed BS, PL and Cash flow.
2	Reversal of Impairment Loss	Prohibits reversal of impairment loss recognised in a previous interim period in respect of goodwill or an investment.	No such Provision
3	Parent's Separate Statements & the Consolidated Financial Statements in the Entity's Interim Report	Neither requires nor prohibits the inclusion of the parent's separate statements in the entity's interim report prepared on a consolidated basis.	It included the consolidated financial statements in addition to the separate financial statements in the interim financial report.

4	Accounting Policies	Ind AS 34 requires requirements of AS 25 plus additionally requires the information in respect of methods of computation followed.	Notes of interim financial statements require, containing a statement that the same accounting policies are followed in the interim financial statements.
5	Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets	Requires information on both contingent liabilities and contingent assets, if they are significant.	Requires information on contingent liabilities only
6	Extraordinary Items	Not Required	Required
7	Change in Accounting Policy	Restatement of prior interim financial statement and annual financial statement.	Restating of prior interim periods financial statement.

Ind AS 36: Impairment of Assets

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 36: Impairment of Assets	AS 28: Impairment of Assets
1	Applies to Financial Assets	Applies to financial assets classified as subsidiaries, joint ventures and associates.	Not Applicable
2	Exclude biological assets	Specifically excludes biological assets related to agricultural activity	Not specifically exclude biological assets
3	Mandatory Annual Impairment Testing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ An intangible asset with an indefinite useful life ➤ Intangible asset not yet available for use ➤ Goodwill acquired in a business combination. 	No annual impairment testing unless there is an indication of impairment.
4	Reversal of Goodwill	Prohibits the recognition of reversals of impairment loss for goodwill.	Reversed in a subsequent period when it was caused by a specific external event
5	Bottom up and Top Down Test	No Bottom up and Top Down Test for allocation of Goodwill.	Bottom up and Top Down Test for allocation of Goodwill.
6	Guidance for the value in use of an asset, using PV techniques	Additional guidelines given.	Brief guidelines given.
7	Disclosures	More Disclosure	Less Disclosure

Ind AS 37: Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 37: Provisions, Contingent Liabilities and Contingent Assets	AS 29: Provisions, Contingent Liabilities & Contingent Assets.
1	Constructive obligations and Change in the Definition of Provision and Obligating Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ "Legal obligation" and "constructive obligation" have been inserted and defined in Ind AS 37. ➤ Provision can be created from Constructive obligation. 	Provision can be created only in case of Business practice.
2	Discounting Provisions	Discounting provisions, if effect of the time value of money is material.	Prohibits discounting the amounts of provisions except in case of decommissioning, restoration and similar liabilities that are recognised as cost of PPE under AS-10.
3	Disclosure of Contingent Assets	Disclosure of contingent assets in the financial statements	Disclosure in the report of the approving authority.
4	Impairment loss	An entity should recognise any impairment loss that has occurred on assets dedicated to Onerous contract.	No Such Provision.

Ind AS 38: Intangible Assets

SN	Basis of Differences	IND AS 38: Intangible Assets	AS 26: Intangible Assets
1	Exclusions	Ind AS 38 does not include any exclusion in relation to accounting for discount or premium relating to borrowings and ancillary costs incurred in.	Does not apply to accounting for discount or premium relating to borrowings and ancillary costs incurred in.
2	Removed from Definition of Intangible Assets	The requirement for the asset to be held for use in the production or supply of goods or services, for rental to others, or for administrative purposes has been removed from the definition.	Included

3	Payment Deferred beyond Normal Credit Terms	Difference between cash amount and the total payments is recognised as interest expense over the period of credit unless it is capitalised in Ind AS 23	No such provision
4	Acquired in Business Combination	Deals in detail in respect of intangible assets acquired in a business combination	Acquired in an amalgamation in the nature of purchase is dealt.
5	Subsequent Expenditure on R&D Project Process	Gives guidance for the treatment of such expenditure	No guidance
6	Intangible Assets Acquired in Exchange	Should be recognised at the fair value of the asset given up.	Fair market value of the asset acquired or surrendered which has more clearly evident.
7	Useful Life.	The useful life can even be indefinite.	Cannot exceed 10 years
8	Valuation Model as Accounting Policy	Permits an entity to choose either the cost model or the revaluation model	Revaluation model is not permitted
9	Legal Life	Useful life shorter than the legal life	No such Provision
10	Change in Method of Amortization	Change in accounting estimate.	Change in accounting policy
11	Annual Impairment Testing	Annual impairment testing of an intangible asset not yet available for use	No such requirement
12	Disclosures	More Disclosure	Less Disclosure

Ind AS 103: Business Combinations

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 103: Business Combinations	AS 14: Amalgamations
1	Scope	A Business combination has a wider scope.	Deals only with amalgamation.
2	Methods for Accounting	Prescribes only the acquisition method for every business combination.	Two methods (a) the pooling of interest method and (b) the purchase method
3	Assets and Liabilities	At fair value under acquisition method	At their existing book values or at fair values under the purchase method
4	Amortisation of Goodwill	Goodwill is not amortised but tested for impairment on annual basis in accordance with Ind AS 36	If amalgamation in the nature of purchase, amortised over a periods not exceeding five years.
5	Contingent Consideration in case of business combination	Deals with an obligation of the acquirer to transfer additional assets or equity interests to the former owners of an acquire if specified future events occur or conditions are met.	Does not provide specific guidance on this aspect.
6	Bargain Purchase Gain	Bargain purchase gain arising on business combination to be recognised in other comprehensive income and accumulated in equity as capital reserve.	The excess amount is treated as capital reserve

Ind AS 105: Non-current Assets Held for Sale and Discontinued Operations

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 105: Non-current Assets Held for Sale and Discontinued Operations.	AS 24: Discontinuing Operations
1.	Scope and Objective	The accounting for non-current assets held for sale, and the presentation and disclosure of discontinued operations	Principles for reporting information about discontinuing operations
2	Cash Flow Statement	Does not mention so.	Requirements related to CFS are applicable when the enterprise presents a CFS
3	Discontinued v/s Discontinuing Operations	A discontinued operation is a component of an entity that either has been disposed of or is classified as held for sale	There is no concept of discontinued operations but it deals with discontinuing operations.
4	Time Period	Within one year from the date of classification with certain exceptions	Does not specify any time period in this regard as it relates to discontinuing operations
5	Initial Disclosure Event	Does not mention so as it relates to discontinued operation.	AS 24 specifies about the initial disclosure event in respect to a discontinuing operation
6	Measurement	Measured at the lower of carrying amount and fair value less costs to sell.	Requires to apply the principles set out in other relevant Accounting Standards
7	Abandonment of Assets is a discontinuing operation	Not classified as a discontinuing operation.	Classified as a discontinuing operation

8	Guidance Regarding Measurement of Changes to a Plan of Change	Provides guidance.	Does not give any specific guidance regarding this aspect
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Ind AS 108: Operating Segments

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 108: Operating Segments	AS 17: Segment Reporting
1	Identification of Segments	Based on 'management approach', whose operating results are regularly reviewed by the entity's chief operating decision maker.	Two sets of segments; Business and Geographical segment based on the risks and returns approach.
2	Measurement of Amounts to be Reported in Segments	On the same basis as that used by the chief operating decision maker for the purposes of allocating resources to the segments and assessing its performance	Segment information to be prepared in conformity with the accounting policies adopted for preparing & presenting the FS.
3	Aggregation criteria.	Two or more segments can be aggregated if they have similar economic characteristics	No specific guidelines
4	Single Reportable Segment	Requires certain disclosures even in case of entities having single reportable segment	Not required to be disclosed. (Disclosed by way of footnote)

Ind AS 28: 'Investments in Associates and Joint Ventures'

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 28 'Investments in Associates and Joint Ventures'	AS 23 'Accounting for Investments in Associates in CFS'
1	Significant Influence	Power to participate in policy decisions but not control or joint control over those policies.	Power to participate in policy decisions but not control over those policies.
2	Potential Voting Rights	Are considered for determining significant influence (SI).	Are not considered for determining SI
3	Accounting of investment in associates in the C&SFS	Equity method should be applied, even if there is no subsidiary.	Equity method, only if there is a subsidiary.
4	Exception to equity method	No exception to equity method	Exceptions to equity method are available
5	Option where a part of the investment in associate is held indirectly through certain specific modes.	The part so held could be measured at fair value. Equity method to be applied to the remaining portion.	No Such exemption
6	Share of losses in entity	Carrying amount of investment with long term interests shall be considered. Discontinue when such carrying amount becomes Nil.	Only carrying amount of interest shall be considered.
7	Loss of SI over an associate	Should be recognized in OCI, and reclassified to SPL on disposal.	No specific guidance
8	Capital reserve/ negative goodwill	Should be recognized directly in equity, on any acquisition	Should be included in carrying amount of associate but disclosed separately.
9	Uniform accounting policies	To be followed unless it is impracticable to do so.	If not practicable, facts to be disclosed.
10	Reporting date	The difference in reporting dates should not be more than 3 months	No specific guidance
11	Impairment	Objective evidence.	Recognize any decline other than temporary.

Ind AS 111- Joint Arrangements

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 111- Joint Arrangements	AS 27- Financial Reporting of Interests in JV
1	Defined Terms	Joint control, Joint arrangement	Joint control, Joint venture
2	Accounting Method	Can either be JO or JV, the classification depends on rights and obligations of parties to arrangement.	Prescribes 3 forms of joint venture: JCO, JCA, JCE.
3	Accounting of interest in jointly controlled entity in the separate financial statements	Accounted for either at cost or as per Ind AS 109. If classified as held for sale, should be accounted for as per Ind AS 105. Equity method should be applied if venture does not prepare separate financial statements	As per AS 13 at cost less provision for other than temporary decline
4	Explanation on the term near future	It is deleted because it is covered under Ind AS 105.	Explanation given in Ind AS27
5	Disclosure of ventures share in post- acquisition reserves of a jointly controlled entity	No specific guidance	Shown separately under the relevant reserve while applying proportionate consolidation method.
6	Accounting in case of JC over an entity which is a subsidiary of the entity.	No recognition of such cases	Consolidated under AS 21.

Ind AS 110 Consolidated Financial Statements

SN	Basis of Differences	Ind AS 110: Consolidated Financial Statements	AS 21 Consolidated Financial Statements
1	Scope	Mandates the preparation of CFS for a Parent	Not mandatory for a parent.
2	Control	Principle based: Investor controls investee when it is exposed or has rights to variable returns from involvement with investee and has ability to affect those returns through its power over investee.	Rule based: ➤ Ownership of more than half voting power. ➤ Control of composition of board
3	Potential Voting Rights	Needs to be considered for control assessment.	Are not considered for control assessment.
4	Uniform Accounting Policies	To be followed and no recognition of situation of impracticability	If not considered for control assessment.
5	Notes to consolidated financial statements	No such clarification	Notes necessary for true & fair view and notes involving material items
6	Exclusion of subsidiary from consolidation	All subsidiaries are consolidated	If subsidiary acquired with intention to dispose of within 12 months or it operates under severe long term restrictions which impair its ability to transfer funds to parent, then subsidiaries need not be consolidated.
7	Treatment in case of more than one parent of a subsidiary	Each investor would account for its interest in the investee in accordance with relevant Ind AS. Such as Ind AS 111, 28, 109	Both need to consolidate the financial statement of that entity as per AS 21.
8	Difference in Reporting Dates	Should not be more than 3 months	Should not be more than 6 months
9	Presentation of minority interest	Should present within equity, separately from the equity of the owners of the parent	Presented separately from liabilities & equity of the parent's shareholder.

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